

Running samples in the rheometer

Step	Task	Images	Comment
	<p>Document title: Running samples in the rheometer</p> <p>Laboratory location: University of Stavanger (UiS)</p> <p>Objective: This procedure describes the laboratory method used to obtain flow curves of model fluids with the rheometer in this thesis work. It includes instrument start-up, geometry installation, measurement of xanthan and carbopol samples, data export, and shutdown and cleaning</p> <p>Assumptions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Defined a project in the rheometer. <p>Information: Rheometer in the laboratory.</p>		
			Initialize the rheometer (start-up of the rheometer)

Step	Task	Images	Comment
1.	Turn on the rheometer by rotating the black power switch from 0 to 1.		0 means it is off. See the picture; this one shows it turned on.
2.	Open the air supply by turning the valve so that it points toward the PC, as shown in the picture.	<p data-bbox="721 1644 1123 1711">The picture shows it turned on, pointing toward the PC.</p>	

Step	Task	Images	Comment
3.	Release the emergency stop by pressing/twisting the red button until the display shows "Off".		
4.	Verify that the upper protective cover / housing is closed, as shown in the picture.		
5.	Verify that no measuring geometry is attached to either the upper or lower measuring position before initialization	<p data-bbox="722 1837 1177 1900">The hole should look like as shown above.</p>	This applies to both the upper cylinder and the lower cylinder as shown in the images.

Step	Task	Images	Comment
6.	On the PC, open the rheometer software by clicking the red RheoCompass icon.		
7.	<p>Verify that it is connected to the following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Current configuration: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Default MCR 702e MultiDrive SN84066114 • Device: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ MCR 702e MultiDrive SN84066114 		

Step	Task	Images	Comment
8.	On the PC, open the rheometer software by clicking the red RheoCompass icon.	<p>The screenshot shows the RheoCompass software interface. A list of lubricants is visible, including 'Lubricants DIN 51810-1, NLGI 2' and 'Lubricants DIN 51810-2'. A 'Hysteresis Area' graph is partially visible at the bottom of the screen.</p>	
9.	Click "Initialize" and wait until "OK" appears on the rheometer display. Initialization is only required when the instrument has been fully shut down.	<p>The screenshot shows the 'Initialize' dialog box in the RheoCompass software. The 'Initialize' button is highlighted. Below it, there are several checkboxes and input fields for system parameters, including 'Temperature (C/P-PTD180/MD): 23.00 °C' and 'C/P-PTD180/MD: CORIO CP-200F'. A 'Hysteresis Area' graph is also visible in the background.</p>	
10.	Type 20 in both fields	<p>A close-up screenshot of the software interface showing the 'Temperature (C/P-PTD180/MD)' field set to 20.00 °C. The 'C/P-PTD180/MD' field is also visible, set to CORIO CP-200F.</p>	
Run the test after initialization			

Step	Task	Images	Comment
1.	<p>For xanthan Use the cylinder/cup measuring system shown in the pictures. Check that both parts are clean before use.</p> <p>For Carbopol use the CP50-1/TI cone and the L-PP50/MD/PTD/T lower measuring plate. Check that both parts are clean before use.</p>		<p>Use the cup/cylinder for xanthan, but for carbopol, which has a gel-like consistency, use a cone-and-plate geometry.</p>
2.	<p>Xanthan For xanthan, pour the sample into the lower cup up to the marked fill line. Wipe away any spilled liquid.</p> <p>Carbopol For carbopol, ensure that the cone-and-plate geometry is clean before mounting.</p>		

Step	Task	Images	Comment
3.	<p>Pull the “Pull to open” mechanism fully outward before inserting the lower measuring part.</p>		
4.	<p>Xanthan Carefully insert the filled lower cup into the rheometer without spilling the sample.</p> <p>Carbopol Mount the lower measuring plate on the rheometer base.</p>		

Step	Task	Images	Comment
5.	<p>Push the lower holder fully inward using "Push to close" until it is completely closed.</p>		

Step	Task	Images	Comment
6.	<p>Xanthan: Carefully insert the upper cylinder into the upper holder. See images.</p> <p>Carbopol: Mount the upper cone component as shown in the figure below.</p>		

Step	Task	Images	Comment
7.	<p>Carefully insert the upper cylinder into the top holder. Before locking it, make sure the mark on the cylinder is aligned with the mark on the holder, as shown in the blue circle.</p>		
8.	<p>Hold the upper cylinder with one hand and pull the locking sleeve downward with the other hand until the cylinder is secured.</p>		

Step	Task	Images	Comment
9.	<p>Verify that the locking sleeve fully covers the top of the cylinder, confirming that it is locked in place.</p>		
10.	<p>Xanthan: Lower the upper cylinder by pressing the down-arrow button with the horizontal line underneath it.</p> <p>Carbopol: After mounting both measuring parts, click "Set zero gap".</p>		

Step	Task	Images	Comment
11.	<p>Carbopol: For carbopol only: remove the upper cone, place the sample in the center of the lower plate, and avoid trapping air bubbles</p>		<p>This step is only related for tests with Carbopol and can be skipped for xanthan</p>
12.	<p>Carbopol: For carbopol only: reinsert the upper cone and repeat the mounting/locking procedure described in Steps 6-9.</p>		<p>This step is only related for tests with Carbopol and can be skipped for xanthan</p>
13.	<p>Carbopol: Trim excess sample around the cone-and-plate geometry using the trimming tool, then click "Continue".</p>	<p>Tool used to trim the sample</p>	<p>This step is only related for tests with Carbopol and can be skipped for xanthan</p>

Step	Task	Images	Comment
14.	<p>Xanthan: For xanthan, verify that the upper cylinder enters the lower cup correctly; a small upward rise of liquid is expected.</p> <p>Carbopol: For carbopol, verify that excess sample has been removed and that the area around the cone is clean.</p>		
15.	Install the two protective covers carefully before running the measurement.		

Step	Task	Images	Comment
16.	In the software, select File > Open.		
17.	<p>Carbopol: For carbopol only: open the method “Preshear - Tale”, run the preshear test, and wait 10 minutes before starting the flow-curve measurement.</p>		See steps 20-24 for how to run the test

Step	Task	Images	Comment
18.	Search for “MF” and open the method “Viscosity test for Glycerol, Xanthan and Carbopol - MF, KM, AL”.		
19.	Click “Start” to begin the measurement sequence.		
20.	Enter a clear and consistent test name and complete the metadata fields before starting the measurement. Include the test number and sample type in the test name. In the fields “Operator,” “Sample,” and “Description,” record the operator name, sample		

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	<p>composition, preparation date, test date, and the measuring geometry used. Use the same naming format for all xanthan and carbopol measurements.</p> <p>Example:</p> <p>Test name: Test 4 – 58/42 Glycerol/Water</p> <p>Operator: MCR 702e, Avar Lalo</p> <p>Sample: Sample prepared on 10 February 2025. Composition: 58 wt% glycerol and 42 wt% water (350 g glycerol and 250 g water). Sample tested on the same day, 10 February 2025.</p> <p>Description: Geometry used: C-CC27 MD/PTD/TS cylinder cup, standard, with MEAS cylinder B-CC27.</p>		
21.	Click “Continue” to start the test.	<p>A screenshot of a software interface. At the top, there are two buttons: 'Abort test' and 'Continue'. The 'Continue' button is circled in red. Below the buttons is a 'Details' section with a 'Default test name' field and a 'Naming strategy' dropdown set to 'Enumerate test name if existing'.</p>	
22.	Monitor the test status in the software. During startup, the software will display “waiting for temperature surveillance”. The remaining test time is shown on screen.	<p>A screenshot of a software interface showing a test status. A green progress bar is visible with the text 'Waiting for temperature surveillance, remaining time: 49 s'. Below it, there is a red warning icon and the text 'Reg/smg fremid 3°C'. At the top of the screen, there is a message: 'Use ribbon "Home" to move tests here from project data tree'.</p>	It will show how much time is remaining to complete the test (the picture shows 49 seconds remaining).

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23.	After the test is complete, open the “Diagram” tab to view the flow-curve results.																																																																																							
24.	Open the “Table” view, right-click in the results table, select “Export”, and save the data locally in the project folder in Excel format.	<table border="1" data-bbox="732 1081 1230 1365"> <thead> <tr> <th>Point No. Nr</th> <th>Shear Rate $\dot{\gamma}$ [1/s]</th> <th>Shear Stress τ [Pa]</th> <th></th> <th></th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr><td>1</td><td>0,1</td><td>0,0010174</td><td></td><td></td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>0,179</td><td>0,001757</td><td></td><td></td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>0,319</td><td>0,0031225</td><td></td><td></td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>0,57</td><td>0,0056076</td><td></td><td></td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>1,02</td><td>0,0099566</td><td></td><td></td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>1,82</td><td>0,01775</td><td></td><td></td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>3,25</td><td>0,031625</td><td></td><td></td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>5,8</td><td>0,056511</td><td></td><td></td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>10,4</td><td>0,10093</td><td></td><td></td></tr> <tr><td>10</td><td>18,5</td><td>0,18046</td><td></td><td></td></tr> <tr><td>11</td><td>33</td><td>0,32321</td><td></td><td></td></tr> <tr><td>12</td><td>59</td><td>0,58128</td><td></td><td></td></tr> <tr><td>13</td><td>105</td><td>1,0503</td><td></td><td></td></tr> <tr><td>14</td><td>188</td><td>1,9085</td><td></td><td></td></tr> <tr><td>15</td><td>336</td><td>3,4901</td><td>10,589</td><td>0,16751 Dy_aut</td></tr> <tr><td>16</td><td>600</td><td>6,4306</td><td>10,717</td><td>0,34513 Dy_aut</td></tr> </tbody> </table>	Point No. Nr	Shear Rate $\dot{\gamma}$ [1/s]	Shear Stress τ [Pa]			1	0,1	0,0010174			2	0,179	0,001757			3	0,319	0,0031225			4	0,57	0,0056076			5	1,02	0,0099566			6	1,82	0,01775			7	3,25	0,031625			8	5,8	0,056511			9	10,4	0,10093			10	18,5	0,18046			11	33	0,32321			12	59	0,58128			13	105	1,0503			14	188	1,9085			15	336	3,4901	10,589	0,16751 Dy_aut	16	600	6,4306	10,717	0,34513 Dy_aut	
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Shut down the rheometer (finished with testing)

Step	Task	Images	Comment
1.	Remove the protective covers.	<p>The top photograph shows a close-up of a hand in a white lab coat pulling a black protective cover off the top of a white Anton Paar instrument. The cover has a red 'X' warning symbol and the text 'PULL TO OPEN' and 'Close cover carefully before measuring'. The bottom photograph shows the instrument with the cover removed, revealing the internal sample chamber and measurement head. The Anton Paar logo is visible on the white upper housing. The instrument is placed on a white table with two red caps and a blue pen nearby.</p>	

Step	Task	Images	Comment
2.	Raise the measuring head by pressing the up-arrow button with the horizontal line underneath it.		
3.	Remove the upper measuring part first. Support it with one hand while releasing the locking sleeve with the other. Remove it carefully to avoid dropping it or spilling sample. For carbopol, remove the upper cone first.	<p>The image shows a person's hand interacting with the upper measuring part of the rheometer. A blue arrow points upwards, indicating the direction of movement. The hand is positioned to support the measuring head while releasing the locking sleeve.</p>	<p>There may be some spillage, so it is best to rinse it first. Same task applies for Carbopol (Cone and plate)</p>

Step	Task	Images	Comment
		<p>The top photograph shows a hand holding a silver metal rod vertically, with its lower end inserted into a circular opening on a black microscope base. The base has two white triangular warning symbols. The bottom photograph shows the same hand holding the rod at an angle, demonstrating its flexibility or how it fits into the base. The background in both images shows a laboratory setting with a microscope and other equipment.</p>	

Step	Task	Images	Comment
4.	Rinse the removed upper measuring part with water immediately after use. For carbopol, dispose of waste liquid in the designated water-based liquid sludge container.	<p>The 'Images' column contains two photographs. The top photograph shows a person's hand holding a cylindrical metal measuring part over a stainless steel sink. The bottom photograph shows the same hand holding the measuring part under a running faucet in the sink, with water spraying over it.</p>	

Step	Task	Images	Comment
5.	Dry the upper measuring part with paper.		
6.	Return the upper measuring part to its storage container and close the lid.		

Step	Task	Images	Comment
7.	Pull the "Pull to open" mechanism fully outward.		
8.	Carefully remove the lower cup / lower measuring part without scraping it against the instrument.		

Step	Task	Images	Comment
		<p>The top photograph shows a hand in a white lab coat sleeve turning the objective turret of a microscope. The turret is black and has a central ring with a small notch. Below the turret, a black plate has the text 'PUSH TO CLOSE' and 'PULL TO OPEN' with arrows. A warning label below that says 'close lower coupling before mounting'. The bottom photograph shows the same hand using a silver screwdriver to adjust the central ring of the turret. The same text and warning label are visible below the turret.</p>	

Step	Task	Images	Comment
9.	Push the holder back in and ensure it is fully closed.		
10.	Rinse the lower cup / lower measuring part with water. Dilute the remaining sample before disposal.		

Step	Task	Images	Comment

Step	Task	Images	Comment
11.	Dry the lower measuring part with paper.		
12.	Return the lower measuring part to its storage box.		

Step	Task	Images	Comment
13.	Close the storage box.	A photograph showing a person's hand holding a stack of several clear plastic storage boxes. The boxes are stacked on top of each other. In the background, there is a desk with a keyboard, a mouse, and some cables.	
14.	Verify that both measuring parts have been removed, stored safely, and that the "Pull to open" mechanism has been pushed back in.	A photograph showing a hand interacting with the front of a microscope. The hand is pulling a lever labeled "PULL TO OPEN". Below the lever, there is a warning label that says "Power coupling before mounting." The microscope has a large lens in the center and two triangular warning symbols on either side.	

Step	Task	Images	Comment
15.	Close the current project in the software.	<p>The image shows a vertical toolbar on the right side of a software window. At the top, there are two project entries: 'Test 2 (60/40 Glycerol)' and 'Test 1 (50% wt Glyce...'. Below these are several icons: a green play button, a blue downward arrow, a blue floppy disk icon, and a yellow folder icon. A tooltip with the text 'Close current project' is pointing to the folder icon.</p>	
16.	Click «Ja» to save	<p>The image shows a 'Save' dialog box with the following text: 'Do you want to save changes in project 'Viscosity Test for Glycerol, Xanthan and Carbopol - MF, KM, AL?'. There are three buttons at the bottom: 'Ja', 'Nei', and 'Avbryt'. The 'Ja' button is highlighted with a mouse cursor.</p>	

Step	Task	Images	Comment
17.	Close the software	A photograph of a computer workstation. The monitor displays two side-by-side images of a monkey's face. A keyboard and mouse are visible on the desk in front of the monitor.	
18.	Turn the black power switch to 0 to switch off the rheometer.	A close-up photograph showing a person's hand turning a black power switch on a piece of white equipment. The switch is currently in the '0' position. A label on the equipment provides technical specifications: '84066114', 'AC 100..230 V', '50..60 Hz', '900 W', and 'MFD 2022'.	
19.	Press the red emergency-stop button until the display shows “- - - -”.	A photograph showing a hand pressing a red emergency-stop button on a white Julabo device. The device has a small digital display and the brand name 'Julabo' is visible.	

Step	Task	Images	Comment
20.	Close the air supply so that the valve points toward the rheometer.		
21.	Return the prepared sample batch to the designated sample storage area.		
22.	Verify that the rheometer display is blank and that the instrument is fully shut down.		
23.	Inspect the work area for spills. Wipe up any residue and return		

Step	Task	Images	Comment
	all equipment and materials to their proper location.		